

Replication instructions for the paper:
From Russia with love: empirical evidence on affiliate
profitability under sanctions and capital flight across
borders

Oleg Gurshev*

January 2025

Replication package comes in two parts: main regression results and graphs:

1. Main regression results (this reproduces all Tables except Table 1, requires STATA and reghdfe package).
 - To reproduce Tables 2, 3, 4, 5, 8, B1 use:
“Gurshev Russia main estimation code.do” and “data_all.dta” files.
 - To reproduce Tables 6, 7 use:
“Gurshev Russia Cyprus.do” and “data_cyprus_and_real_only.dta” files.
2. Graphs.rar (this reproduces all graphs, requires R, both scripts will check for required packages and install them for you).
 - To reproduce Figures A1-A9 use:
“Gurshev Russia histograms.R” and .csv files from the folder “Graphs”.
 - To reproduce Figures A10-A13 use:
“Gurshev Russia line graphs.R” and .csv files from the folder “Graphs”.
 - Table 1 data can be found:
“Graphs/data” folder, file “avg_own_all.csv” (see total averages).

Note: other information such as more detailed data on firms (e.g. specific names of owners, location inside Russia, sales, and etc.) or code used for accounting raw data can be obtained via request to the author. All of accounting data come from ORBIS, scope: 2012-2019.

*Contact: oleggurshev@gmail.com